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Review Article

Natural Treatments for Liver Conditions: A Review on Phytochemicals and Hepatoprotective Plants

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ABSTRACT

One of the most important organs in the body is the liver. The liver being a very important organ of the body depends on the food we take, which is agreeable to an extent. The functions performed by the liver include regulating numerous processes such as the metabolism, secretion, storage, and detoxification of chemicals whether internal or external. Liver diseases remain among the major threats to public health and continue being a problem worldwide. Despite the significant advances made in medicine, there are no drugs that can offer full protection for the liver, improve its functioning or contribute to the formation of new liver cells. Therefore, it is necessary to look for other drugs that could be used to effectively treat liver diseases. Plants have played a crucial role in human healthcare. Scientific investigations have proven that the beneficial effects of the plants are provided by phytochemicals contained in them. The main objective of the present study was to summarize data obtained from scientific research regarding the use of several plants that are often consumed by humans, including spirulina, chamomile, silymarin, and cactus pear (nopal) as well as its fruits demonstrating hepatoprotective properties, and the investigation of a resin (propolis) as well as several phytochemicals isolated from plants, yeasts, and algae examined in hepatotoxicity models.

INTRODUCTION

1.1. The significance of the liver

The regulation of several physiological functions is dependent on the functioning of the liver, which in turn is associated with several vital functions like metabolism, secretion, and storage^{1,2}. There

have been many studies conducted since the 1970s regarding the capacity of the liver to produce helpful substances as well as detoxify other substances of organisms.

1.2 The Liver's Primary Functions

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The metabolic processes of growth, nutrition, energy, and reproduction are also carried out by the liver. It also helps with bile secretion, vitamin storage, and the metabolism of fats and carbs.

1.3 Public Health Issues and Liver Diseases

Hepatic disorders remain among the major risks to public health owing to all of the aforementioned functions, and they are a worldwide phenomenon. Damage to the liver cells, tissues, structure, or its functions is termed "hepatic disease" and can be caused by biological organisms such as bacteria, viruses, and parasites, along with autoimmune disorders like primary biliary cirrhosis and immune hepatitis, as well as the effect of various agents, including drugs (paracetamol (PCM) and antitubercular drugs in large amounts), toxins (carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄), thioacetamide, dimethylnitrosamine (DMN), D-galactosamine/lipopolysaccharide (GalN/LPS)), and certainly excessive consumption of alcohol³⁻⁵. Despite significant advancements in contemporary medicine, there are currently no medications that fully preserve the liver, promote hepatic cell regeneration, or increase hepatic activity⁶⁻¹⁰. Furthermore, certain medications have negative side effects. In order to treat hepatic illnesses, it is therefore vital to find alternative medications that are less harmful and more effective.

1.4. Fruits and Plants' Potential for Medicine

Human health care has been greatly influenced by the use of some plants. The traditional medicine, which is predominantly composed of plant materials, has been practiced as a form of medical treatment for more than 80% of the world population. Phytochemicals can be defined as biologically active substances or chemical compounds that do not form an essential part of nutrition for survival. Several studies conducted

on medicinal plants and consumption of fruits have proved that these properties might be accountable for their beneficial role. There have been several scientific studies conducted on certain phytochemicals on the effect they have on health. Some of the most frequently discussed examples include: (1) anthocyanins (cranberries), (2) betalain pigments (betanin and indica xanthine), (3) vinca alkaloids (vincristine, vinblastine and vindesine), and (4) resveratrol, all these have generally been studied in relation to their chemoprotective characteristics against cancer.

All therapeutic plants and the consumption of particular fruits have had various effects on biological systems. Most studies have concentrated on studying their sedative, analgesic, antipyretic, cardioprotective, antibacterial, antiviral, antiprotozoal, and anticarcinogenic properties despite other studies conducted on their hepatoprotective nature.

1.5. Hepatoprotective herbs

The traditional medicine, which is predominantly composed of plant materials, has been practiced as a form of medical treatment for more than 80% of the world population¹¹⁻¹⁵. Phytochemicals can be defined as biologically active substances or chemical compounds that do not form an essential part of nutrition for survival. Several studies conducted on medicinal plants and consumption of fruits have proved that these properties might be accountable for their beneficial role¹⁶⁻¹⁹. There have been several scientific studies conducted on certain phytochemicals on the effect they have on health. Some of the most frequently discussed examples include: (1) anthocyanins (cranberries), (2) betalain pigments (betanin and indica xanthine), (3) vinca alkaloids (vincristine, vinblastine and vindesine), and (4) resveratrol, all these have generally been studied in relation to

their chemoprotective characteristics against cancer²⁰⁻²¹.

All therapeutic plants and the consumption of particular fruits have had various effects on biological systems. Most studies have concentrated on studying their sedative, analgesic, antipyretic, cardioprotective, antibacterial, antiviral, antiprotozoal, and anticarcinogenic properties despite other studies conducted on their hepatoprotective nature²².

1.5.1. *Annona squamosa*

Histological examination showed that the hepatotoxic group possessed portal triaditis associated with hepatocyte necrosis and inflammation in the centrilobular region. In the therapy group, lobular pattern was normal and they exhibited mild portal triaditis and low inflammation²³⁻²⁶. Another study evaluated the protection against hepatotoxicity induced by diethyl nitrosamine. From this study, it was clear that extracts from *Annona squamosa* have hepatoprotective effects and may serve as a potential therapy for liver injury due to chemicals²⁷⁻³⁰.

1.5.2. *Silybum marianum*

The protection provided by the polyphenolic extracts of *Silybum marianum* and *Cichorium intybus* against the toxicity of the liver induced was evaluated by thioacetamide³¹⁻³³. Both plants were injected into rats at a dosage of 25 mg kg⁻¹ of body weight, while the thioacetamide dosage was 50 mg kg body weight. Rats administered both extracts and thioacetamide displayed a marked decrease in bilirubin, alkaline phosphatase, and aminotransferase activity as compared to the rats administered thioacetamide only. No major changes were observed in terms of the amount of Na⁺, K⁺ or the liver weight in the different groups.

In view of the flavonoid content of the extracts and their antioxidant properties, the experiments indicated that *Silybum marianum* and *Cichorium intybus* had a hepatoprotective effect³⁴⁻³⁷.

1.5.3. *Chamomile capitula*

To evaluate the potential mechanism of hepatoprotection, the influence of an ethanolic extract of *Chamomile recutita capitula* (400 mg kg⁻¹, P.O.) on glutathione levels, Na⁺ K⁺-ATPase enzyme activity, serum marker enzymes, serum bilirubin levels, glycogen levels, and thiobarbutiric acid reactive substances against the effect of paracetamol induced hepatotoxicity in rats. It is observed that the extract of *Chamomile recutita* showed reverse effects on all these parameters against paracetamol-induced hepatotoxicity³⁸⁻⁴⁰.

1.5.4. *Coccinia grandis*

Hepatotoxic rats exposed to CCl₄ were administered an alcoholic extract of fruits from *Coccinia grandis* Linn (Curcubitaceae), and the concentrations of AST, ALT, ALP, total proteins, and total and direct bilirubin were evaluated. The alcoholic extract was found to have a hepatoprotective activity at the dose of 250 mg/kg through a marked (p<0.05) decrease in blood enzyme activities (AST, ALT, and ALP) and bilirubin, similar to that of silymarin⁴¹⁻⁴⁴.

1.5.5. *Wedelia calendulacea*

The ethanolic extract of *Wedelia calendulacea* L. (Asteraceae family) was examined for its hepatoprotective action on acute toxicity induced by CCl₄ in rats.

The results showed that *Wedelia calendulacea* ethanolic extract exhibited dose-dependent reduction in serum enzymes activity induced by CCl₄ along with elevation of total protein and bilirubin content, which indicated the capability of

the extract to enhance the normal functional status of the liver as well as rats. The weight of the organs including liver, heart, lung, spleen, and kidney increased significantly with administration of ethanolic extract of *Wedelia calendulacea* in mice having impaired liver function due to CCl₄⁴⁵⁻⁴⁸.

1.5.6. *Prostechea michuacana*

Prostechea michuacana (PM) extracts in methanol, hexane, and chloroform were studied for their anti-liver damage activity in CCl₄-induced liver damage in albino rats. Pretreatment of methanolic extract reduced the biochemical parameters of liver damage activity and demonstrated dose-dependent inhibition of *in vivo* peroxidation caused by CCl₄. In addition, pretreatment of PM extracts against paracetamol-induced hepatotoxicity and its possible mechanism of action were evaluated in rats after administering PM extracts at doses of 200, 400, and 600 mg/kg⁴⁹⁻⁵³. The blood biochemical analysis was carried out to evaluate the degree of protection offered. It was found that methanolic extract of orchid had a pronounced hepatoprotective activity, indicated by decreased enzyme and bilirubin activities in the serum. Thus, these results suggested that the methanolic extract of *Prostechea michuacana* could prevent paracetamol-induced lipid peroxidation, thereby eliminating the harmful effects of toxic metabolites of paracetamol.

1.5.7. *Aegle marmelos*

In the Indian medical system, leaves of *Aegle marmelos* (Bael), which belong to the Rutaceae family, were used as herbal drugs.

The essential marker biochemical parameters were used for evaluation of the hepatoprotective potential of *Aegle marmelos* on liver injury induced by ethanol in rats. The results revealed that Bael leaves are highly hepatoprotective.

Similar results were also obtained by other investigators⁵⁴⁻⁵⁸.

1.5.8. *Cassia roxburghii*

Seeds from *Cassia roxburghii* DC have been utilized in the treatment of various diseases affecting the liver as a result of the hepatoprotective properties of the seeds. In rats, the toxicity induced by ethanol-CCl₄ mixture was effectively reversed in a dose-dependent manner by methanolic extract of *Cassia roxburghii*.

This extract produces actions that are comparable to Liv-52® which is one of the most known hepatoprotective drugs from plants⁵⁹⁻⁶³.

1.5.9. *Orthosiphon stamineus*

The hepatoprotective activity of *O. stamineus* methanol extract against paracetamol induced hepatic damage in rats has been assessed. The biochemical parameters such as AST, ALT, ALP, and lipid peroxidation have been determined for the animals treated with paracetamol as well as for the untreated group. From the results obtained it appears that the treatment with 200 mg/kg body weight of *O. stamineus* leaf methanolic extract accelerates the recovery of altered biochemical parameters towards normal in a dose-dependent manner⁶⁴⁻⁶⁸.

1.5.10. *Ficus carica*

The methanolic extract of the leaves of *Ficus carica* Linn. (Moraceae) was evaluated for its possible hepatoprotective effect using rats with CCl₄-induced liver damage. Significant reductions were noted in serum AST, ALT, total serum bilirubin, and malondialdehyde equivalents (a measure of lipid peroxidation of liver cells) following oral administration of the extract at 500 mg/kg⁶⁹⁻⁷³.

1.5.11. *Lepidium sativum*

The protective effect of the methanol extract of *Lepidium sativum* at doses of 200 and 400 mg/kg against the harmful effects of carbon tetrachloride-induced hepatic injury in rats was evaluated⁷⁴⁻⁷⁹. Groups that received treatment with *Lepidium sativum* demonstrated significant reduction in all biochemical indices. In the groups that received *Lepidium sativum*, the extreme fatty changes observed in the livers of rats due to CCl₄ were insignificant.

1.5.12. *Sargassum polycystum*

Rats suffering from D-galactosamine induced hepatitis were employed for assessing the preventative efficacy of *Sargassum polycystum* ethanol extract. D-Galactosamine induced increases in the concentrations of diagnostic markers (AST, ALT and ALP) in the plasma of rats were markedly (P<0.05) reduced following the administration of *S. polycystum* extract orally [125 mg/kg body weight/day for 15 days]. By inhibiting the activation of lipid peroxidation and preserving the hepatic antioxidant defense system near normal level, it is also demonstrated antioxidant activity against D galactosamine induced hepatitis. *Sargassum polycystum* has potent anti-hepatotoxic activity due to its antioxidant and membrane stabilizing effects⁸⁰⁻⁸⁴.

1.5.13. *Solanum nigrum*

The effects of *Solanum nigrum* extract (SNE) on hepatic fibrosis in mice caused by thioacetamide (TAA) were investigated. Throughout the course of the trial, mice in the three TAA groups received daily gastrogavage treatments of distilled water and SNE (0.2 or 1.0 g/kg). In TAA-treated animals, SNE decreased the levels of α -smooth muscle actin protein and hepatic hydroxyproline. Growth factor- β 1 TGF- β 1 RNA levels in the liver

were transformed by SNE's inhibition of TAA-induced collagen α 1) (I). Additionally, histological analysis verified that SNE lessened the amount of fibrosis brought on by TAA therapy. Oral SNE administration dramatically lessens TAA-induced hepatic fibrosis in rats, most likely via lowering TGF- β 1 seretio⁸⁵⁻⁸⁷.

In another investigation, rats with chronic hepatotoxicity caused by CCl₄ were used to test the preventive effects of aqueous extract of SN (ASNE) against liver damage. The findings demonstrated that ASNE treatment considerably reduced the CCl₄-induced blood levels of hydroxyl radicals, superoxide, and hepatic enzyme indicators. According to liver histology, ASNE decreased the frequency of liver diseases in rats, such as hazy swelling of the liver cells, lymphocyte infiltration, hepatic necrosis, and fibrous connective tissue growth brought on by CCl₄. Thus, the study's findings imply that ASNE may shield rats' livers from oxidative damage caused by CCl₄. This hepatoprotective effect may be attributed to ASNE's modulation of detoxification enzymes as well as its antioxidant and free radical scavenging properties⁸⁸⁻⁹⁰. DNA is protected from oxidative damage to its deoxyribose sugar moiety by the addition of plant extracts of *Solanum nigrum* and *Cichorium intybus* in the processing mixture including calf thymus DNA and a free radical producing apparatus. The concentration of plant extracts had an impact. On the other hand, *Cichorium intybus* had a far stronger effect than *Solanum nigrum*. According to these investigations, the ability of these crude plant extracts to inhibit the oxidative destruction of DNA in the tissue debris may be the cause of the observed hepatoprotective effect⁹¹⁻⁹⁴. Given that these herbs are widely recognized as hepatoprotective agents and have demonstrated their effectiveness in preventing CCl₄-induced liver injury⁹⁵⁻⁹⁷, it is possible that their

effectiveness can be linked to their capacity to scavenge free radicals.

Table 1: Mechanism of herbal sources exhibiting hepatoprotective action

Sr. No.	Plant/Herbal Source	Experimental Model	Dose/Extract Used	Key Findings	Proposed Mechanism
1	Annona squamosa	Diethyl nitrosamine-induced hepatotoxicity	Plant extract	Reduced hepatocytic necrosis, portal triaditis, and centrilobular inflammation; restored normal lobular architecture	Antioxidant and hepatoprotective activity against chemical-induced liver injury
2	Silybum marianum	Thioacetamide-induced hepatotoxicity in rats	Polyphenolic extract, 25 mg/kg	Significant reduction in bilirubin, ALP, and aminotransferase levels	Flavonoid-mediated antioxidant and membrane stabilizing effect
3	Chamomile recutita	Paracetamol-induced hepatotoxicity	Ethanol extract of capitula, 400 mg/kg (P.O.)	Restored glutathione, Na ⁺ /K ⁺ -ATPase activity, glycogen, bilirubin, and serum marker enzymes	Hepatostimulant action with antioxidant potential
4	Coccinia grandis	CCl ₄ -induced hepatotoxicity	Alcoholic fruit extract, 250 mg/kg	Reduced AST, ALT, ALP, and bilirubin levels comparable to silymarin	Hepatocellular membrane protection and antioxidant effect
5	Wedelia calendulacea	Acute CCl ₄ -induced hepatotoxicity	Ethanol extract	Dose-dependent normalization of serum enzymes and bilirubin; improved organ weight changes	Restoration of normal liver function and antioxidant activity
6	Prostecchia michuacana	CCl ₄ and paracetamol-induced hepatotoxicity	Methanol extract, 200–600 mg/kg	Reduced serum enzymes, bilirubin, and lipid peroxidation	Prevention of toxic metabolite-induced oxidative stress
7	Aegle marmelos	Alcohol-induced liver damage	Leaf extract	Significant hepatoprotective activity with restoration of biochemical markers	Antioxidant and liver regenerative properties
8	Cassia roxburghii	Ethanol-CCl ₄ -induced hepatotoxicity	Methanolic seed extract, 250 and 500 mg/kg	Dose-dependent reversal of hepatotoxicity similar to Liv-52®	Hepatotoxin modulation and antioxidant activity
9	Orthosiphon stamineus	Paracetamol-induced hepatotoxicity	Methanol leaf extract, 200 mg/kg	Restored AST, ALT, ALP, and lipid peroxide levels near normal	Antioxidant-mediated recovery of hepatic tissue

10	Ficus carica	CCl4-induced hepatotoxicity	Methanolic leaf extract, 500 mg/kg	Significant reduction in AST, ALT, bilirubin, and lipid peroxidation	Free radical scavenging and hepatocellular protection
11	Lepidium sativum	CCl4-induced hepatotoxicity	Methanolic extract, 200 and 400 mg/kg	Decreased biochemical markers and reduced fatty liver changes	Antioxidant and anti-steatotic effects
12	Sargassum polycystum	D-galactosamine-induced hepatitis	Ethanol extract, 125 mg/kg/day for 15 days	Reduced AST, ALT, ALP and lipid peroxidation; maintained antioxidant defense system	Membrane stabilization and antioxidant action
13	Solanum nigrum	TAA and CCl4-induced hepatotoxicity/fibrosis	Aqueous extract and SNE (0.2–1.0 g/kg)	Reduced fibrosis, TGF- β 1 expression, hydroxyproline, oxidative stress, and hepatic necrosis	Antifibrotic, antioxidant, free radical scavenging, and detoxification enzyme modulation
14	Cichorium intybus	Oxidative DNA damage and hepatotoxicity models	Plant extract	Strong inhibition of oxidative DNA damage and hepatoprotection	Potent antioxidant and DNA protective activity

Table 2: Summary of Hepatoprotective Plants and Their Major Pharmacological Actions

Pharmacological Action	Plants Showing Activity
Antioxidant activity	Silybum marianum, Solanum nigrum, Sargassum polycystum, Aegle marmelos
Reduction of serum liver enzymes (AST, ALT, ALP)	Coccinia grandis, Orthosiphon stamineus, Ficus carica
Anti-inflammatory activity	Annona squamosa, Solanum nigrum
Antifibrotic activity	Solanum nigrum
Prevention of lipid peroxidation	Prostechea michuacana, Ficus carica, Sargassum polycystum
Membrane stabilizing effect	Silybum marianum, Sargassum polycystum
Restoration of normal liver histology	Lepidium sativum, Annona squamosa
DNA protective/free radical scavenging effect	Solanum nigrum, Cichorium intybus

Table 3: Comparative Overview of Experimental Hepatotoxicity Models

Hepatotoxic Agent	Mechanism of Toxicity	Plants Evaluated
CCl4	Lipid peroxidation and oxidative stress	Coccinia grandis, Wedelia calendulacea, Lepidium sativum, Ficus carica, Solanum nigrum
Paracetamol	Toxic metabolite (NAPQI)-induced oxidative damage	Chamomile recutita, Orthosiphon stamineus, Prostechea michuacana
Thioacetamide (TAA)	Hepatic necrosis and fibrosis	Silybum marianum, Solanum nigrum
D-galactosamine	Hepatic inflammation and oxidative stress	Sargassum polycystum
Diethyl nitrosamine	Chemical-induced hepatocellular injury	Annona squamosa
Ethanol + CCl4	Combined oxidative and inflammatory liver damage	Cassia roxburghii
Alcohol	Chronic oxidative liver injury	Aegle marmelos

DISCUSSION

At least 25% of patients with liver problems use ethnobotanicals, and the use of herbal medicines is growing worldwide. In order to solve the mysteries surrounding the plants, more work needs to be done on methodological scientific evaluation for their safety and efficacy through rigorous preclinical investigations and clinical trials. By standardizing the dosing regimen based on evidence-based findings, this strategy will assist explore the true therapeutic efficacy of these natural pharmacotherapeutic substances and go beyond a passing fad⁹⁸. There are numerous herbal remedies available to promote health, reduce symptoms, and treat illnesses. Nevertheless, scientific pharmacological confirmation is lacking for the majority of these products. Several herbal remedies showed hepatoprotective and curative properties in laboratory or higher animals' experimental hepatotoxicity models, which calls for their clinical study. The majority of herbal formulations cannot be recommended for the treatment of liver problems due to a lack of scientifically supported pharmacological data⁹⁹⁻¹⁰⁰.

Only four terrestrial plants have been scientifically explained while adhering to internationally recognized scientific protocols, despite the fact that Indian systems of medicine have more than 300 preparations (using more than 87 Indian medicinal plants) for the treatment of jaundice and chronic liver diseases. Extensive research has demonstrated *Sylibum marianum*'s anti-oxidative, anti-lipid peroxidative, antifibrotic, anti-inflammatory, immunomodulating, and liver-regenerative properties. It has been demonstrated that *Glycyrrhiza glabra* is both endogenous interferon-producing and hepatoprotective.

CONCLUSION

Liver cirrhosis and drug-induced liver injury rank as the ninth most common cause of mortality in both western and developing nations, making chronic hepatic illnesses one of the biggest health issues in the world. Western medicine-based therapies are frequently ineffective, have the potential to have negative side effects, and are excessively expensive, particularly for developing nations. Therefore, it seems quite appealing to treat liver illnesses with readily available plant-derived chemicals that don't require time-consuming pharmaceutical production. The reported hepatoprotective plants from India and other countries have been compiled in this review article, which may be helpful to medical professionals, scientists, and academics working in the fields of pharmacology and therapeutics to develop evidence-based alternative medicine to treat various liver diseases in humans and animals.

REFERENCES

1. Epidemiológico B. Sistema Nacional de Vigilancia Epidemiológica. Sistema Único de Información. 2017;34:1-68. Available in: <https://www.gob.mx/cms/uploads/attachment/file/182221/sem01.pdf>
2. Hadzagic-Catibusic F., Hasanbegovic E., Melunovic M., Zubcevic S., Uzicanin S. Effects of carbamazepine and valproate on serum aspartate aminotransferase, alanine aminotransferase and gamma-glutamyltransferase in children. Med. Arch. 2017;71:239–242. doi: 10.5455/medarh.2017.71.239-242. [DOI] [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
3. Devarbhavi H., Asrani S.K., Arab J.P., Nartey Y.A., Pose E., Kamath P.S. Global burden of liver disease: 2023 update. J. Hepatol. 2023;79:516–537. doi:

- 10.1016/j.jhep.2023.03.017. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
4. GBD Collaborators Disease and Injury Incidence and Prevalence Collaborators Global, regional, and national incidence, prevalence, and years lived with disability for 354 diseases and injuries for 195 countries and territories, a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study. *Lancet*. 2017;392:1789–1858. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(18)32279-7. [DOI] [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
 5. Yang K., Chen J., Zhang T., Yuan X., Ge A., Wang S., Xu H., Zeng L., Ge J. Efficacy and safety of dietary polyphenol supplementation in the treatment of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Front. Immunol.* 2022;13:949746. doi: 10.3389/fimmu.2022.949746. [DOI] [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
 6. Targher G., Tilg H., Byrne C.D. Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease: A multisystem disease requiring a multidisciplinary and holistic approach. *Lancet Gastroenterol. Hepatol.* 2021;6:578–588. doi: 10.1016/S2468-1253(21)00020-0. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
 7. Panahi Y., Kianpour P., Mohtashami R., Atkin S.L., Butler A.E., Jafari R., Badeli R., Sahebkar A. Efficacy of artichoke leaf extract in non-alcoholic fatty liver disease: A pilot double-blind randomized controlled trial. *Phytotherapy Res.* 2018;32:1382–1387. doi: 10.1002/ptr.6073. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
 8. Englisch W., Beckers C., Unkauf M., Ruepp M., Zinserling V. Efficacy of Artichoke dry extract in patients with hyperlipoproteinemia. *Arzneimittelforschung.* 2020;50:260–265. doi: 10.1055/s-0031-1300196. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
 9. Majnooni M.B., Ataee M., Bahrami G., Heydarpour F., Aneva I.Y., Farzaei M.H., Ahmadi-Juoibari T. The effects of co-administration of artichoke leaf extract supplementation with metformin and vitamin E in patients with nonalcoholic fatty liver disease: A randomized clinical trial. *Phytother. Res.* 2021;35:6324–6334. doi: 10.1002/ptr.7279. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
 10. Musolino V., Gliozzi M., Bombardelli E., Nucera S., Carresi C., Maiuolo J., Mollace R., Paone S., Bosco F., Scarano F., et al. The synergistic effect of Citrus bergamia and Cynara cardunculus extracts on vascular inflammation and oxidative stress in non-alcoholic fatty liver disease. *J. Tradit. Compl. Med.* 2020;10:268–274. doi: 10.1016/j.jtcme.2020.02.004. [DOI] [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
 11. Fogacci F., Rizzoli E., Giovannini M., Bove M., D’addato S., Borghi C., Cicero A.F.G. Effect of Dietary Supplementation with Eufortyn® Colesterolo Plus on Serum Lipids, Endothelial Reactivity, Indexes of Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease and Systemic Inflammation in Healthy Subjects with Polygenic Hypercholesterolemia: The ANEMONE Study. *Nutrients.* 2022;14:2099. doi: 10.3390/nu14102099. [DOI] [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
 12. Nejati L., Movahedi A., Salari G.R., Moeineddin R., Nejati P. The Effect of Berberine on Lipid Profile, Liver Enzymes, and Fasting Blood Glucose in Patients with Non-alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD): A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Med. J. Islam. Repub. Iran.* 2022;36:294–301. doi: 10.47176/mjiri.36.39. [DOI] [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
 13. Harrison S., Gunn N., Neff G., Kohli A., Liu L., Flyer A., Goldkind L., Bisceglie A. A phase 2, proof of concept, randomised controlled trial of berberine ursodeoxycholate in patients with presumed non-alcoholic steatohepatitis and type 2 diabetes. *Nat. Commun.* 2021;12:5503. doi: 10.1038/s41467-021-25701-5. [DOI] [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
 14. Marzban M., Bahrami M., Kamalinejad M., Tahamtan M., Khavasi N., Haji-Monfared M., Jameshorani M. The therapeutic effects of chicory seed aqueous extract on cardio-metabolic profile and liver enzymes in

- nonalcoholic fatty liver disease; a double blind randomized clinical trial. *Immunopathol. Persa.* 2022;10:e28262. doi: 10.34172/ipp.2022.28262. [DOI] [Google Scholar]
15. Parveen F., Siddique M.A., Quamri M.A., Khaleel A., Nayak T., Mariyam A. Cichorium Intybus and Solanum Nigrum leave juice (Murawwaquain) reduces raised Liver Enzymes and improved conditions associated with Hepatobiliary Diseases: A Single Blinded, Pre and Post Analytical Study. *Int. J. Res. Anal. Rev.* 2020;7:659–668. [Google Scholar]
 16. Ghaffari A., Rafrat M., Navekar R., Sepehri B., Asghari-Jafarabadi M., Ghavami S.-M. Turmeric and chicory seed have beneficial effects on obesity markers and lipid profile in non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) *Int. J. Vitam. Nutr. Res.* 2019;89:293–302. doi: 10.1024/0300-9831/a000568. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
 17. Al-Amarat W, Abukhalil MH, Alruhaimi RS, Alqhtani HA, Aldawood N, Alfwuaires MA, Althunibat OY, Aladaileh SH, Algefare AI, Alanezi AA (2022) Upregulation of Nrf2/HO-1 signaling and attenuation of oxidative stress, inflammation, and cell death mediate the protective effect of apigenin against cyclophosphamide hepatotoxicity. *Metabolites* 12:648
 18. Chalasani NP, Maddur H, Russo MW, Wong RJ, Reddy KR. ACG clinical guideline: diagnosis and management of idiosyncratic drug-induced liver injury. *Am J Gastroenterol.* 2021;116:878–98. <https://doi.org/10.14309/ajg.0000000000001259>.
 19. Hayashi PH, Bjornsson ES. Long-term outcomes after drug-induced liver injury. *Curr Hepatol Rep.* 2018;17:292–9. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11901-018-0411-0>.
 20. Shen T, Liu YX, Shang J, Xie Q, Li J, Yan M, Xu JM, Niu JQ, Liu JJ, Watkins PB, Aithal GP, Andrade RJ, Dou XG, Yao LF, Lv FF, Wang Q, Li YG, Zhou XM, Zhang YX, Zong PL, Wan B, Zou ZS, Yang DL, Nie YQ, Li DL, Wang YY, Han XA, Zhuang H, Ma YM, Chen CW. Incidence and etiology of drug-induced liver injury in mainland China. *Gastroenterology.* 2019;156:2230–41. <https://doi.org/10.1053/j.gastro.2019.02.002>.
 21. Yang XM, Shen BR, Liu PY, Yang KN, Zhao Q, Wang ZK. Logistic regression analysis of risk factors of antituberculosis drug-induced liver injury. *Chin J Hospital Pharm.* 2019;39:67–71. <https://doi.org/10.13286/j.cnki.chinhospfarmacyj.2019.01.15>.
 22. Xiong XM, Li L, Wang B. Progress in genetic polymorphism of drug-induced liver injury. *Chin J Hospital Pharm.* 2020;40:827–30. <https://doi.org/10.13286/j.1001-5213.2020.07.23>.
 23. Yang S, Hwang SJ, Park JY, Chung EK, Lee JI. Association of genetic polymorphisms of CYP2E1, NAT2, GST and SLCO1B1 with the risk of anti-tuberculosis drug-induced liver injury: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMJ Open.* 2019;9: e027940. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2018-027940>.
 24. Zhang CY, Jiao L, Bai H, Zhao ZZ, Hu XJ, Wang MJ, Wu T, Peng W, Liu TYH, Song JJ, Zhou J, Li MJ, Lyv MY, Zhang JW, Chen H, Chen J, Ying BW. Association of POR and PPAR α polymorphisms with risk of anti-tuberculosis drug-induced liver injury in Western Chinese Han population. *Infect Genet Evol.* 2020;79: 104147. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.meegid.2019.104147>.
 25. Zhang L, Zhu JY. Research progress of anti tuberculosis drug-induced liver injuries. *Jiangxi Med J.* 2019;54(9):1139–41. <https://doi.org/10.3969/j.issn.1006-2238.2019.9.049>.
 26. Yan X, Deng Y, Ma J, Li PJ, Yang ZJ, Yang XJ, Zhou Y. Research advance in mechanism of cisplatin toxic injury and its prevention and treatment by traditional chinese medicine. *Chin J Exp Tradit Med Formulae.* 2021;27(5):233–42. <https://doi.org/10.13422/j.cnki.syfjx.20202460>.

27. Wang W, Bai MR, Jiang T, Li C, Li P, Zhou H, Wang ZM, Li LP, Jiang HD. Clozapine-induced reduction of l-carnitine reabsorption via inhibition/down-regulation of renal carnitine/organic cation transporter 2 contributes to liver lipid metabolic disorder in mice. *Toxicol Appl Pharmacol.* 2019;363:47–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.taap.2018.11.007>.
28. Zhang HN, Zhou YF, Liu JB, Pang QH. Exploring protective effects and mechanisms of quercetin on liver injury based on both NF- κ B and Nrf2 signaling pathways. *Acta Agric Boreali Occidentalis Sinica.* 2020;29(1):143–9. <https://doi.org/10.7606/j.issn.1004-1389.2020.01.017>.
29. Du YC, Zhang H, Zhong FR, Chen HL, Lai L, Qian B1, Peng T, Xia XM, Fu WG. Protective effect of pinocembrin in a mouse model of liver injury induced by acetaminophen. *J Clin Hepatol.* 2020;36(3):608–11. <https://doi.org/10.3969/j.issn.1001-5256.2020.03.027>.
30. Wang XX, An JH, Wang ZL. Protective effect of total flavonoids extracted from *Polygonum perfoliatum* L. on the liver injury caused by anti-tuberculosis drugs in mice. *Chin J Clin Pharmacol.* 2021;37:713–7. <https://doi.org/10.13699/j.cnki.1001-6821.2021.06.017>.
31. Du YC, Zhang H, Zhong FR, Chen HL, Lai L, Qian BL, Tan P, Xia XM, Fu WG. Protective effect of pinocembrin in a mouse model of liver injury induced by acetaminophen. *J Clin Hepatol.* 2020;36:608–11. <https://doi.org/10.3969/j.issn.1001-5256.2020.03.027>.
32. Ahmad MM, Rezk NA, Fawzy A, Sabry M. Protective effects of curcumin and silymarin against paracetamol induced hepatotoxicity in adult male albino rats. *Gene.* 2019;712: 143966. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gene.2019.143966>.
33. Gao YQ, Zhou ZH, Shan JJ. The effect of natural polysaccharides on drug-induced liver injury: research advances. *J Int Pharm Res.* 2019;46:163–70. <https://doi.org/10.13220/j.cnki.jipr.2019.03.001>.
34. Qian L, Liu Y, Li BX, Fu J, Li WY, Cao N, Tian YB, Xu DN. Polysaccharide of *Atractylodes macrocephala* koidz may alleviate liver injury induced by cyclophosphamide via toll-like receptor 4 signaling pathway in goslings. *J Ani Nutr.* 2019;31:764–74. <https://doi.org/10.3969/j.issn.1006-267x.2019.02.033>.
35. Abenavoli, L., Izzo, A. A., Milić, N., Cicala, C., Santini, A., and Capasso, R. (2018). Milk thistle (*Silybum marianum*): a concise overview on its chemistry, pharmacological, and nutraceutical uses in liver diseases. *Phytother. Res.* 32, 2202–2213. doi: 10.1002/ptr.6171
36. Balderramo, D., Prieto, J., Diehl, F., Gonzalez-Ballerga, E., Ferreiro, M., Carrera, E., et al. (2018). Sorafenib for treatment of hepatocellular carcinoma: a survival analysis from the south american liver research network. *J. Clin. Gastroenterol.* doi: 10.1097/MCG.0000000000001085. [Epub ahead of print].
37. Bischoff, K., Mukai, M., and Ramaiah, S. K. (2018). “Liver toxicity,” in *Veterinary Toxicology*, 3rd Ed, ed R. C. Gupta (Breathitt Veterinary Center, Murray State University, Hopkinsville, KY: Elsevier), 239–257. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-811410-0.00015-5
38. Al-Snafi AE. Pharmacological effects and therapeutic properties of *Hibiscus cannabinus*- A review. *Indo Am J P Sc* 2018; 5 (4): 2176-2182. [200]. Al-Snafi
39. AE. Chemical constituents, pharmacological effects and therapeutic importance of *Hibiscus rosasinensis*- A review. *Journal of Pharmacy* 2018; 8 (7): 101-119.
40. Al-Snafi AE. Chemical constituents, nutritional, pharmacological and therapeutic importance of *Juglans regia*- A review. *IOSR Journal of Pharmacy* 2018; 8(11): 1-21.
41. Moon, A.M.; Singal, A.G.; Tapper, E.B. Contemporary epidemiology of chronic liver disease and cirrhosis. *Clin. Gastroenterol.*

- Hepatol. 2020, 18, 2650–2666. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef] [PubMed]
42. Oztumer, C.A.; Chaudhry, R.M.; Alrubaiy, L. Association between behavioural risk factors for chronic liver disease and transient elastography measurements across the UK: A cross-sectional study. *BMJ Open Gastroenterol.* 2020, 7, e000524.
 43. Ma, Y.; Lee, G.; Heo, S.Y.; Roh, Y.S. Oxidative stress is a key modulator in the development of nonalcoholic fatty liver disease. *Antioxidants* 2021, 11, 91.
 44. Villanueva-Paz, M.; Morán, L.; López-Alcántara, N.; Freixo, C.; Andrade, R.J.; Lucena, M.I.; Cubero, F.J. Oxidative stress in drug-induced liver injury (DILI): From mechanisms to biomarkers for use in clinical practice. *Antioxidants* 2021, 10, 390.
 45. Yuan, W.; Wang, J.; An, X.; Dai, M.; Jiang, Z.; Zhang, L.; Yu, S.; Huang, X. UPLC-MS/MS Method for the Determination of Hyperoside and Application to Pharmacokinetics Study in Rat After Different Administration Routes. *Chromatographia* 2021, 84, 249–256
 46. Wang, Q.; Wei, H.C.; Zhou, S.J.; Li, Y.; Zheng, T.T.; Zhou, C.Z.; Wan, X.H. Hyperoside: A review on its sources, biological activities, and molecular mechanism. *Phytother. Res.* 2022, 36, 2779–2802.
 47. Zhang, Y.; Yu, X.; Wang, M.; Ding, Y.; Guo, H.; Liu, J.; Cheng, Y. Hyperoside from *Z. bungeanum* leaves restores insulin secretion and mitochondrial function by regulating pancreatic cellular redox status in diabetic mice. *Free Radic. Biol Med.* 2021, 162, 412–422
 48. Mapoung, S.; Umsumarng, S.; Semmarath, W.; Arjsri, P.; Srisawad, K.; Thippraphan, P.; Yodkeeree, S.; Dejkriengkraikul, P. Photoprotective Effects of a Hyperoside-Enriched Fraction Prepared from *Houttuynia cordata* Thunb. on Ultraviolet B-Induced Skin Aging in Human Fibroblasts through the MAPK Signaling Pathway. *Plants* 2021, 10, 2628.
 49. Liu, J.; Zhang, Z.; Yang, L.; Fan, Y.; Liu, Y. Molecular structure and spectral characteristics of hyperoside and analysis of its molecular imprinting adsorption properties based on density functional theory. *J. Mol. Graph.* 2019, 88, 228–236.
 50. Saçıcı, E.; Yesilada, E. Development of new and validated HPTLC methods for the qualitative and quantitative analysis of hyperforin, hypericin and hyperoside contents in *Hypericum* species. *Phytochem. Anal.* 2022, 33, 355–364.
 51. Zhang, X.; Su, J.; Wang, X.; Wang, X.; Liu, R.; Fu, X.; Li, Y.; Xue, J.; Li, X.; Zhang, R. Preparation and Properties of Cyclodextrin Inclusion Complexes of Hyperoside. *Molecules* 2022, 27, 2761.
 52. Xing, H.; Fu, R.; Cheng, C.; Cai, Y.; Wang, X.; Deng, D.; Gong, X.; Chen, J. Hyperoside protected against oxidative stress-induced liver injury via the PHLPP2-AKT-GSK-3 β signaling pathway in vivo and in vitro. *Front. Pharmacol.* 2020, 11, 1065.
 53. Cai, Y.; Li, B.; Peng, D.; Wang, X.; Li, P.; Huang, M.; Xing, H.; Chen, J. Crml-Dependent Nuclear Export of Bach1 is Involved in the Protective Effect of Hyperoside on Oxidative Damage in Hepatocytes and CCl₄-induced Acute Liver Injury. *J. Inflamm. Res.* 2021, 14, 551–565.
 54. Abd Rashid, N.; Abd Halim, S.A.S.; Teoh, S.L.; Budin, S.B.; Hussan, F.; Ridzuan, N.R.A.; Jalil, N.A.A. The role of natural antioxidants in cisplatin-induced hepatotoxicity. *Biomed. Pharmacother.* 2021, 144, 112328.
 55. Liou, G.G.; Hsieh, C.C.; Lee, Y.J.; Li, P.H.; Tsai, M.S.; Li, C.T.; Wang, S.H. N-Acetyl cysteine overdose inducing hepatic steatosis and systemic inflammation in both propacetamol-induced hepatotoxic and normal mice. *Antioxidants* 2021, 10, 442.
 56. Hu, C.; Chen, Y.; Cao, Y.; Jia, Y.; Zhang, J. Metabolomics analysis reveals the protective effect of quercetin-3-O-galactoside (Hyperoside) on liver injury in mice induced by acetaminophen. *J. Food Biochem.* 2020, 44, e13420.

57. Guo, X.; Zhu, C.; Liu, X.; Ge, Y.; Jiang, X.; Zhao, W. Hyperoside protects against heart failure-induced liver fibrosis in rats. *Acta Histochem.* 2019, 121, 804–811
58. Guo, X.; Qu, F.; Xin, Y.; Wang, J.; Li, H.; Ma, A.; Zhao, W. Effect and mechanism of hyperin on liver fibrosis in rats with heart failure. *Shandong Yi Yao* 2021, 61, 40–45.
59. Abdelhameed, R.F.; Ibrahim, A.K.; Elfaky, M.A.; Habib, E.S.; Mahamed, M.I.; Mehanna, E.T.; Darwish, K.M.; Khodeer, D.M.; Ahmed, S.A.; Elhady, S.S. Antioxidant and Anti-Inflammatory Activity of *Cynanchum acutum* L. Isolated Flavonoids Using Experimentally Induced Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus: Biological and In Silico Investigation for NF- κ B Pathway/miR-146a Expression Modulation. *Antioxidants* 2021, 10, 1713.
60. Guan, X.; Zhao, W.; Min, D.; Liu, C.; Shang, Y.; Hu, L. Protective effect of hyperoside on non-alcoholic fatty liver disease in ApoE^{-/-} mice induced by high-fat diet. *Drug Eval. Res.* 2022, 45, 281–286
61. Ding, W.X.; Yang, L. Alcohol and drug-induced liver injury: Metabolism, mechanisms, pathogenesis and potential therapies. *Liver Res.* 2019, 3, 129–131.
62. Lian, C.Y.; Zhai, Z.Z.; Li, Z.F.; Wang, L. High fat diet-triggered non-alcoholic fatty liver disease: A review of proposed mechanisms. *Chem.-Biol. Interact.* 2020, 330, 109199.
63. Sun, B.; Zhang, R.; Liang, Z.; Fan, A.; Kang, D. Hyperoside attenuates non-alcoholic fatty liver disease through targeting Nr4A1 in macrophages. *Int. Immunopharmacol.* 2021, 94, 107438.
64. Duan, J.Y.; Chen, W.; Zhao, Y.Q.; He, L.L.; Li, E.C.; Bai, Z.H.; Wang, Y.J.; Zhang, C.P. Flavonoids from *Hypericum patulum* enhance glucose consumption and attenuate lipid accumulation in HepG2 cells. *J. Food Biochem.* 2021, 45, e13898.
65. Wang, S.; Sheng, F.; Zou, L.; Xiao, J.; Li, P. Hyperoside attenuates non-alcoholic fatty liver disease in rats via cholesterol metabolism and bile acid metabolism. *J. Adv. Res.* 2021, 34, 109–122.
66. Elagib H. M., Shadad S. A., Muddathir A. E., Mohammed Y. O., and Elagib S. M., Hepatoprotective activity of the methanolic extract of the bark of *Khaya senegalensis* in rats against carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄) - induced hepatotoxicity in adose of (800 mg/kg I.P), *International Journal of Science and Research.* (2014) 3, no. 3, 1–9.
67. Elagib H. M., Shadad S. A., Muddathir A. E., Mohammed Y. O., and Elagib S. M., Hepatoprotective activity of the methanolic extract of the bark of *Khaya senegalensis* in rats against paracetamol—induced hepatotoxicity, *International Journal of Science and Research.* (2014) 3, no. 3, 127–134.
68. Shama S., Adam I. Y., Marwa M., and Alhameed I. A., *Kigelia africana* fruits' extracts anti hepato-toxic effects on male wistar rats liver destruction induced by CCL₄, *Asian Journal of Medical Sciences.* (2013) 5, no. 1, 26–32, <https://doi.org/10.19026/ajms.5.5342>.
69. Mohamed M., Eldin I., Mohammed A., and Hassan H., Effects of *Lawsonia inermis* L. (Henna) leaves' methanolic extract on CCl₄-induced hepatotoxicity in rats, *Journal of Intercultural Ethnopharmacology.* (2016) 5, no. 1, <https://doi.org/10.5455/jice.20151123043218>, 2-s2.0-85014158913.
70. Adam G. O., Rahman M. M., Lee S.-J. et al., Hepatoprotective effects of *Nigella sativa* seed extract against acetaminophen-induced oxidative stress, *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Medicine.* (2016) 9, no. 3, 221–227, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apjtm.2016.01.039>, 2-s2.0-84960103955.
71. Ahmed B. A., Mohamed A. H., Ali S. A., and Abuelgasim A. I., Hepatoprotective activity of ethanol extract of *Ocimum basilicum* against CCl₄-induced hepatotoxicity in albino rats, *Journal of Natural and Medical Sciences.* (2015) 16, no. 2, 11–18.
72. Ali S., Mohamed A. H., Mohammed G. E., and Gameel A. A., Toxicity of *Balanites aegyptiaca* seeds oil in wistar albino rats,

- SUST Journal of Agricultural and Veterinary Sciences. (2017) 18, no. 1.
73. K. L. Mankani, V. Krishna, B. K. Manjunatha, S. M. Vidya, S. D. Jagadeesh Singh, Y. N. Manohara, Anees-Ur Raheman, K. R. Avinash, Evaluation of hepatoprotective activity of stem bark of *Pterocarpus marsupium* Roxb., *Indian J Pharmacol*, June 2005, Vol 37, Pg No. 165-168.
 74. Wahid A Mulla, Vijay R Salunkhe & Satish B Bhise, Hepatoprotective activity of hydroalcoholic extract of leaves of *Alocasia Indica* (Linn.), *Indian Journal Of Experimental Biology*, October 2009, Vol-47, Pg No. 816- 821.
 75. Nasrin Aghela, Iran Rashidib And Amir Mombeinia, hepatoprotective activity of *Capparis Spinosa* Root Bark against CCl₄ induced hepatic damage in mice, *Iranian Journal Of Pharmaceutical Research* (2007), 6 (4): 285-29.
 76. B. Ganga Rao, N. Jaya Raju*, Investigation Of hepatoprotective activity of *Spondias pinnata*, *International Journal of Pharma Sciences and Research*, Vol.1 (3), 2010, 193-198.
 77. Nahid Tabassum, Shyam S. Agrawal, hepatoprotective activity of *Embelia ribes* against paracetamol induced acute hepatocellular damage in mice, *Experimental Medicine*, 2003, Vol-10, 43-44.
 78. Ayman F. Abdel-Razika*, Abdel-Samid I. Elshamya, Mahmoud I. Nassara, Salah M. El-Kousyb, Hanaa Hamdyc, Chemical Constituents And Hepatoprotective Activity Of *Juncus Subulatus*, 2009, Pg No. 70-84.
 79. V.V.ASHA, Preliminary Studies On The Hepatoprotective Activity Of *Mamordica Subangulata* And *Naragamia Alata*, *Indian Journal Of Pharmacology* 2001; Vol-33, Pg No. 276- 279
 80. Nahid Tabassum, Sushma Chattervedi, S. S Aggrawal, Nissar Ahmed, Hepatoprotective Studies On *Phyllanthus Niruri* On Paracetamol Induced Liver Cell Damage In Albino Mice, *Experimental Medicine*, October-December 2005, Vol-12, Pg.No-211-212
 81. C. Maheswari, R. Maryammal And R. Venkatanarayanan, Hepatoprotective Activity Of “*Orthosiphon Stamineus*” On Liver Damage Caused By Paracetamol In Rats, *Jordan Journal Of Biological Sciences*, September. 2008, Volume 1, Pages 105 -108.
 82. H. Madani, M. Talebolhosseini, S. Asgary and G. H. Naderi, Hepatoprotective activity of *Silybum marianum* And *Clchorium Intybus* against Thioacetamide In Rats, *Pakistan Journal of Nutrition*, 2008, Vol-7(1), Pg No.-172-176.
 83. Nirmal K. Neoliya, Yogendra N. Shukla, Mamta Mishra, Hepatoprotective Activity of *Sarcostemma Brevistigma* Against Carbon tetrachloride-Induced Hepatic Damage In Rats *current Science*, Vol. 84, No. 9, 10 May 2003
 84. Chaudhari N. B., Chittam K. P., Patil V. R., Hepatoprotective Activity Of *Cassia Fistula* Seeds against paracetamol induced hepatic injury in rats, *Arch Pharm Sci & Res* Vol 1 No 2 218 - 221 October 2009.
 85. Singaravel Sengottuvelu, Duraisamy Srinivasan, Rasilingam Duraisami, Jothivel Nandhakumar, Mani Vasudevan And Thangavel Sivakumar, hepatoprotective activity of *Trianthema Decandra* on CCl₄ induced hepatotoxicity on rats, *International Journal Of Green Pharmacy*, Oct-17 2010, Pg No-122-125.
 86. J. Anbu Jeba Sunilson, P. Jayaraj, M. Syam Mohan, A. Anitha Gnana Kumara, R. Varatharajan, Antioxidant And Hepatoprotective Effect Of The Roots Of *Hibiscus Esculentus* Linn., *International Journal Of Green Pharmacy*, Oct-17 2010, Pg No-200-203.
 87. Ramnik Singh, Harwinder Singh Rao, Hepatoprotective Effect Of The Pulp/Seed Of *Aegle Marmelos Correa Ex Roxb* Against Carbontetrachloride Induced Liver Damage In Rats, *International Journal Of Green Pharmacy*, Oct-17 2010, Pg No-232-234.
 88. M. Mujeeb, V. Aeri., P. Bagri, S. A. Khan, Hepatoprotective Activity Of Methanolic Extract Of *Tylophora Indica* (Burm.F.) Merrill.

- Leaves, International Journal Of Green Pharmacy, Oct-17 2010, Pg No-125-127.
89. Md. Rajib Ahsan, Km Monirul Islam, Israt Jahan Bulbul, Md. Ashik Musaddik, Ekramul Haque, Hepatoprotective Activity Of Methanol Extract Of Some Medicinal Plants Against Carbon Tetrachloride-Induced Hepatotoxicity In Rats, European Journal Of Scientific Research, 2009, Vol.37(2), 302-310
 90. Ganesan R, Venkatanarasimhan M, Sharad P, Pramod reddy G, Anandan T and Masilamani G: Hepatoprotective effect of *Coldenia procumbens* linn against Dgalactosamine induced acute liver damage in rats. International Journal of Integrative sciences, Innovation and Technology 2013; 2(2): 9-11.
 91. Prabhakaran V, Srinivas Ashok Kumar B, Sheshadri Shekar D, Nandeesh R, Subramanyam P and Ranganayakulu D: Evaluation of the hepatoprotective activity of *Portulaca oleracea* L. on D-galactosamineinduced hepatic injury in rats. Boletín Latinoamericano y del Caribe de Plantas Medicinales y Aromáticas 2010; 9(3): 199-205.
 92. Duraiswamy B, Satish kumar MN, Gupta S, Rawat M, Om Porwal and Murugan R: Hepatoprotective activity of *Betula utilis* bark on D-galactosamine induced hepatic insult. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences 2012; 1(1): 456-471.
 93. Dhanabal P, Syamala, Elango K and Suresh B: Protective and Therapeutic Effects of the Indian Medicinal Plant *Pterocarpus santalinus* on D-Galactosamine-induced Liver Damage. Asian Journal of Traditional Medicines 2007; 2(2): 51-57.
 94. Dhanabal SP, Rahul Jain, Priyanka DL, Muruganantham N and Raghu PS: Hepatoprotective activity of *Santolina chamaecyparissus* Linn against D-Galactosamine Induced Hepatotoxicity in Rats. Pharmacognosy Communications 2012; 2(2): 67-70.
 95. Dhanabai SP, Syamala G, Satish Kumar MN and Suresh B: Hepatoprotective activity of the Indian medicinal plant *Polygala arvensis* on D-galactosamine-induced hepatic injury in rats. Fitoterapia 2006; 77(6): 472-474.
 96. Jaishree V and Shrishailappa B: Antioxidant and hepatoprotective effect of *Swertiamarin* from *Enicostemma axillare* against D-galactosamine induced acute liver damage in rats. Journal of Ethanopharmacology 2010; 130(1): 103-106.
 97. El-Banna H, Soliman M and Al-wabel N: Hepatoprotective Effects of *Thymus* and *Salvia* Essential oils on Paracetamol-Induced Toxicity in Rats. Journal of Physiology and Pharm acology Advances 2013; 3(2): 41- 47.
 98. Sabir SM, Ahmad SD, Hamid A, Khan MQ, Athayde ML, Santos DB, Boligon AA and Rocha JBT: Antioxidant and Hepatoprotective activity of ethanolic extract of leaves of *Solidago microglossa* containing polyphenolic compounds. Food Chemistry 2012; 131(3): 741-747
 99. Parmar HB, Das SK and Gohil KJ: Hepatoprotective activity of *Macrotyloma uniflorum*. Seed extract on paracetamol and d-galactosamine induced liver toxicity in albino rats. International Journal of Pharmacological Research 2012; 2(2): 86-91.
 100. Vishal BJ, Vishnu NT, Anupama AS, Avinash DD and Suresh RN: Hepatoprotective activity of *Luffa acutangula* against CCl₄ and rifampicin induced liver toxicity in rats: A Biochemical and histopathological evaluation. Indian Journal of Experimental Biology 2010; 48(8): 822-829.

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